

Title: Navigating Cultural Identity: Nigerian Music, Technology, and Social Integration in Lethbridge, Alberta

1. Introduction

My research examines how Nigerian immigrants in Lethbridge, Alberta, use music to establish a sense of emplaced identity, home, and belonging in the diaspora. Lethbridge is a city of 100,000 people situated in Southern Alberta, one hour north of the US-Canada border. I focus on the challenges of Nigerian music-making in this small Canadian city, the creative use of technology, DJing, and amateur musicianship to address them, and the ways these practices foster social integration within the Nigerian community and with other local groups.

My findings draw on ethnographic fieldwork I conducted in 2024 for my master's thesis, the first study to investigate the musical lives of Nigerian migrants in Alberta, particularly southern Alberta. By centering the voices of Nigerian immigrants in Lethbridge, the project fills a gap in scholarship on music, migration, and belonging in this underrepresented region.

2. Nigeria, “japa,” and Lethbridge

Nigeria is a country of over 237 million people, comprising more than 300 ethnic groups and over 500 native languages, with Hausa, Igbo, and Yoruba as the three largest groups. Despite this rich cultural and musical heritage, recent years have seen accelerated out-migration, widely referred to as “japa” in Yoruba (meaning “to escape”), driven by unemployment, high inflation, unequal wealth distribution, and ongoing governance problems since independence.

Canada has become a major destination within this broader African migration, with Nigerians ranking among the top four source countries of new permanent residents and the top African source country in recent immigration reports. Alberta alone is home to over 20,000 Nigerian immigrants, and at least 260 residents of Lethbridge identified as having Nigerian “ethnic or cultural origin” in the 2021 census, though events I attended suggest that the local Nigerian community now numbers in the hundreds. Lethbridge’s educational, agricultural, and governmental sectors, along with its growing visible-minority population, provide opportunities that attract Nigerian migrants as students and workers.

3. Literature: music, migration, diaspora, and well-being

3.1 Migration, diaspora, and identity

In my literature review, I begin by situating migration as both a structural and personal process. Jha and Singh describe migration as arising from “exceptional moments” in a society’s life, often traceable to underlying economic dynamics, which fits the Nigerian “japa” context where socio-economic pressures and political violence push citizens to seek futures elsewhere. Olowere’s definitions of first- and second-generation migrants underscore the importance of generation for how families understand their movement and trace their “generational tree.” This

is what I encountered in conversations with Nigerians in Lethbridge who identified themselves by generation.

Zeleza conceptualizes diaspora as both a state of being and a process of becoming, located in the shifting “interstices of ‘here’ and ‘there,’” thereby capturing the everyday negotiation between Nigerian and Canadian identities in Lethbridge. Eze’s discussion of Africans being “torn between the culture of [their] birth and the domineering influence of Western culture,” neither wholly African nor wholly European, highlights the identity tensions that many migrants must navigate. Cornoş emphasizes that migration affects the entire system of family, professional, cultural, ethnic, and political relations, demanding adaptation to new norms, languages, and social environments. These frameworks help explain why Nigerians in Lethbridge attach such importance to community events and to music as a way of holding together a changing sense of self.

3.2 Music, diaspora, and social integration

Scholars working on music and migration show that music is central to how migrants manage these tensions. Kasinitz and Martiniello argue that migrants frequently know the music of their destination before its language, and hosts often encounter newcomers’ music before knowing much else about them, suggesting that music is an early and powerful site of contact between migrants and the host society. In my own travels to South Africa and Ghana, I experienced how learning local songs became a first step to understanding language and culture, an experience that resonates with Nigerian immigrants’ use of music in Canada.

Frishkopf, writing on refugees and asylum seekers, notes that music and performing arts can link displaced people to each other, to their host societies, and to their homelands, thereby empowering communities, catalyzing social integration, and maintaining personal identity. This echoes what I observed in Lethbridge, where music simultaneously binds Nigerians together, connects them with local Canadian contexts, and keeps them tethered to memories of Nigeria. At the same time, Cassali’s work on immigrant musicians reminds us that they face barriers such as limited audiences, discrimination, and lack of resources, but that these constraints can spark creativity and resilience. The scarcity of professional musicians and instruments in Lethbridge becomes precisely such a catalyst for innovation.

3.3 Music, cultural identity, and emotional well-being

My literature review also considers how music supports cultural identity and emotional well-being among migrants. Scholars such as Liu and Flores Rodriguez describe music as a “bridge” that connects immigrants to their homeland and traditions, providing spaces where community members can gather, share food, celebrate festivals, and transmit language and values to younger generations. Oehrle argues that music promotes intercultural communication, broadens outlooks on the world’s peoples, and breaks down barriers and prejudices, moving communities toward a “culture of tolerance,” which is important in multiethnic contexts like Lethbridge.

Work by Yudkin, Heshmat, and others shows that music activates cognitive, psychomotor, and especially affective domains, offering stress relief, pleasure, and therapeutic benefits. Studies synthesized in my thesis indicate that participation in musical events can enhance immune response, self-efficacy, and social connectedness, while music therapy is used clinically to improve mental health and reduce pain. Ruud further argues that music is a tool for expressing experiences of migration, displacement, and belonging, and for challenging stereotypes and prejudices. These were my own experiences as a new immigrant who relies on music to cope with the emotional challenges of relocation, and they frame my argument that Nigerian musical practices in Lethbridge are crucial for migrants' well-being.

3.4 Nigerian music and adaptation among immigrants

Given the centrality of Nigeria to the study, my literature review outlines how Nigerian music functions as a “force of a living spirit” that shapes behaviour, personality, and identity, as Okafor (through Kush) suggests. Scholars like Nnamani emphasize that traditional music fosters cultural development, community, and continuity, nurturing children and adults through the life course. In diaspora, these musics become key resources for maintaining heritage and passing it on to new generations, even as contemporary Afro-pop draws on traditional styles and Western influences.

Scholars of immigrant music note that migration leads to adaptation and evolution of musical practices as migrants mix home and host styles and respond to new constraints and opportunities. This literature provides a framework for understanding the creative uses of technology, one-person bands, and DJ culture among Nigerians in Lethbridge as forms of adaptation rather than simple loss.

4. Methods and fieldwork

Given these theoretical perspectives, I adopted an ethnographic fieldwork design for my study. Fieldwork combined participant observation at community events, such as Ndi Igbo Day (New Yam Festival), the Tehillah concert, Nigerian Independence Day, church gatherings, and birthday parties, with interviews of five Nigerian community members. These events allowed me to observe how music is embedded in social life, how people participate, and how technology and DJing are deployed in practice.

The interviewees were: a community leader and long-time resident, Moji Taiwo; Lethbridge-based DJ Peter Ntigne (DJ Rav-P); UK-based gospel artist Joel “Fretless” Olubunmi; singer Oreoluwa Akanbi; and singer Victor Olayioye. Their narratives trace the development of the Nigerian community in Lethbridge from the 1970s, the growth of events and associations, and the evolving role of music in community building. My own participation as a violinist and music director at Tehillah 3.0 gave me insight into the practical challenges of organizing Nigerian-style performances with limited resources.

5. Challenges of Nigerian music-making in Lethbridge

My fieldwork confirmed that it is difficult to practice Nigerian music in Lethbridge as it would be practiced in Nigeria. There are a few accomplished Nigerian musicians in Canada, and no

resident professional musicians in Lethbridge, which means that professional Nigerian musicians must be brought in from other cities, provinces, or countries at a high cost. As a result, ensembles are often built around students with competing schedules, and events like Tehillah must adjust repertoires and arrangements at the last minute when musicians are unavailable.

There is also limited access to traditional Nigerian instruments. Fretless's account of arriving for Tehillah and discovering that no drummer and no talking drum were available illustrates how these shortages shape performance, forcing artists to improvise and re-imagine arrangements. Venue issues compound these constraints: church spaces are central gathering points but have limited capacity and equipment, while larger venues offer better staging but reduce the intimacy and free movement, which constrain interactive worship and dancing that characterize many Nigerian worship and party contexts.

These concrete challenges illustrate the literature's discussion of the structural obstacles faced by immigrant musicians, including limited resources and audiences, but also set the stage for the creative solutions being developed, opening space for immigrant-centered practices of self-recognition and resurgence that move beyond the limits of liberal state-based recognition.

6. Technology, DJing, and amateur musicianship

My central argument is that Nigerian immigrants in Lethbridge respond to these constraints by relying on technology, DJing, and amateur musical labour to cultivate a sense of home and community. Non-professional community members take up musical roles in churches and at social events, playing instruments, leading worship, and organizing ensembles when professional musicians are unavailable. For example, a one-person band I observed combined shekere, talking drum, and voice with loop pedals, creating layered textures that evoked juju, highlife, and afrobeat within a single performer's setup.

Loop stations and digital percussion tracks are used in church services and concerts to substitute for full rhythm sections, allowing musicians to build complex grooves despite the absence of full bands. At Tehillah 3.0, Fretless used loop devices and pre-recorded beats to approximate the sonic fullness of Nigerian gospel music, while live instruments and congregational singing interacted with these digital layers.

During the Nigerian Independence Thanksgiving service, keyboard players and singers performed over rhythmic loops, creating an atmosphere that felt recognizably Nigerian to participants.

DJ culture has become important. DJ Rav-P plays a central role at birthday parties, weddings, and the Ndi Igbo festival, curating mixes that span Nigerian music from the 1960s to contemporary Afro-pop. At a 50th-birthday party I attended, DJ Rav-P took over from the One-Person live band and propelled the event deep into the night, with guests dancing enthusiastically and "spraying" money in appreciation, mirroring practices in Nigeria. At Ndi Igbo Day, He used tracks rich in Igbo percussion and call-and-response vocals, helping to sonically mark the event as specifically Igbo even without a live traditional ensemble.

Interviewees emphasize that social media and streaming platforms further reshape diasporic musical life. Victor explains that where there used to be a delay of months before new Nigerian songs reached the diaspora, platforms like YouTube now provide immediate access, meaning Lethbridge playlists can closely track current Nigerian trends. In this sense, technology does more than fill gaps; it collapses distance and time, embedding Lethbridge Nigerians in real-time transnational musical networks, in line with broader literature on adaptation and evolution among immigrant musics.

7. Music, daily life, and social integration

In everyday life, these practices make music a cultural pillar and adaptive mechanism for Nigerians in Lethbridge. Community events like children's first-birthday parties, Tehillah concert, Nigerian Independence Day, and Ndi Igbo Day are saturated with Nigerian music and are eagerly anticipated by immigrants and Nigerian-Canadians alike. At these gatherings, people dress in Nigerian attire, greet each other in Yoruba, Igbo, and pidgin English, and dance to familiar songs, creating a strong sense of "home away from home."

My observations show that such events support emotional well-being and intergenerational continuity, especially in religious and social settings. Children see and hear Nigerian musical practices modeled in Canada, while older migrants find comfort in sonic reminders of home, echoing literature on music's role in memory, coping, and healing. These gatherings also illustrate Oehrle's argument that music can break down cultural barriers and foster a culture of tolerance: Nigerians from different ethnic, religious, and class backgrounds come together as a minority community in Lethbridge, often forming relationships that would be less likely in Nigeria itself.

Events like the Tehillah concert and Nigerian Independence Day tend to reduce ethnic boundaries and divisions that exist back home, temporarily foregrounding a shared Nigerian identity; by contrast, Ndi Igbo Day foregrounds specifically Igbo heritage while still taking place in a broader Canadian context. In both cases, music structures how people move between ethnic identities and a more general diasporic Nigerian identity, aligning with literature that sees music as a key site for negotiating identity, belonging, and connection to home. These events are also open to non-Nigerian guests, meaning that Nigerian music becomes a bridge to other local groups in Lethbridge.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study shows that Nigerian immigrants in Lethbridge use music as a primary means of navigating cultural identity and achieving social integration in the diaspora. Through musical gatherings, they create a sense of home away from home, maintain intergenerational ties, and form networks that cut across ethnic, religious, and class lines. Events such as Tehillah and Nigerian Independence Day reduce the ethnic boundaries that are prominent in Nigeria, while Ndi Igbo Day demonstrates how specific ethnic identities are also preserved.

While technology and DJing occasionally support these practices, the central story is about music itself as a cultural pillar and social force that structures everyday life and belonging. As

the first study to document Nigerian musical practices in southern Alberta, this research contributes to scholarship on music, migration, and diaspora by highlighting how a relatively small immigrant community uses music to negotiate culture, identity, and integration in a Canadian city.

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